

Reactions of certain rice cultivars to sheath rot disease

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A field trial in the 1977 kar season (July–October) observed the reactions of 130 rice cultivars to sheath rot caused by *Acrocyndrium oryzae* by natural infection at earhead maturity stage. Six of the rices were completely disease free (see table) and 18 were relatively resistant, with disease incidence ranging from 2.4 to 20.0%. AS 5127 showed the maximum disease incidence (89%). The incidence in the rest of the cultivars ranged from 0 to 20%. **W**

Reaction of rice varieties to sheath rot disease. Tamil Nadu state, India.

Rice cultivar	Disease incidence (%)
AS 5821	0
AS 6975	0
AS 2992	0
Cult. 1287	0
Cult. 3226	0
Cult. 6403	0
Cult. 2692	2
AS 2572	3
Cult. 643	4
AD 5983	5
AS 2522	7
AS 5277	8
CRM 95-15-12-4	8
AS 5250	9
CR95-721-3	10
AS 6479	12
CR15-7-392-11-4	13
Cult. 1145	14
AS 2444	14
AS 2887	15
AD 6148	15
AD 608	19
AS 4417	19
CR 94-214	20
AS 5127	89

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GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Insect resistance

Evaluation of the 1977 International Rice Stem Borer Nursery at IRRI

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The International Rice Stem Borer Nursery (IRSBN) of the International Rice Testing Program was first conducted in 1976. The 1977 IRSBN consists of 83 entries submitted by rice scientists from 4 countries. Seed sets have been sent to 10 countries.

At IRRI, the 1977 IRSBN was evaluated against the striped borer *Chilo suppressalis* and the yellow stem borer *Tryporyza incertulas*. For the striped borer test, two replicates of two rows, each consisting of 20 hills, were planted. The IRSBN was infested by allowing adults reared from larvae and from eggs that had been placed on an early planted, susceptible variety to oviposit on the test entries. Deadhearts were counted at 60 days after transplanting (DT). In the

yellow borer test, three replicates of 2 rows, each consisting of 20 plants, were transplanted. At 30 DT 5 newly hatched larvae were placed on each plant with a camel's hair brush. At 75 DT deadhearts were counted.

No entry had a high level of resistance. Several entries had intermediate resistance to one of the stem borer species but only a few had intermediate resistance to both (see table). Entries showing the most resistance had about 50% fewer deadhearts than the susceptible check. The lines IET 2845, IET 5540, and IRI 820-52-2 also had intermediate levels of resistance against the stem borer population, which was predominantly *Chilo polychrysus* in the 1976 IRSBN planted in Thailand.

No entry in the yellow borer test was significantly more resistant than the resistant check IR1820-52-2. A few lines in the striped borer test were only slightly better than the resistant check W1263. Thus, no sources with high levels of resistance to the two stem borers are

Entries in the 1977 IRSBN that had intermediate levels of resistance against both *Tryporyza incertulas* and *Chilo suppressalis*. IRRI greenhouse, 1977.

IRTP entry no.	Designation	Cross	Deadhearts (%)	
			<i>T. incertulas</i> 75DT ^a	<i>C. suppressalis</i> 60 DT
10	IET 2845	TKM6/IR8	23	32
26	IET 5540	IR22/NP30	20	36
33	IR1514 A-E666	IR20/TKM6	19	29
36	IR2328-491-1-1-1	IR8//IR8/Dawn//IR8/KAK/4/K8 Mut.	20	35
38	IR2798-143-3-2	IR1529-680/IR1913-41/IR1514 A-E666	21	36
47	IR4791-89	IR3342/IR3341	21	30
55	IR5201-122-2	IR1820-52-2/IR2061464-2	18	35
65	CR157-392-4	Vijaya/Ptb 10	20	37
72	IR3941-97-1	CR126-42-5/IR2061-213	17	31
75	IR36	IR1561//IR24/ <i>Oryza nivara</i> ///CR94-13	19	35
	Resistant checks			
	IR1820-52-2	IR1539-60/IR1416-128-5-19	19	
	W 1263			45
	Susceptible check			
	Rexoro		52	72

^aDays after transplanting.

currently available for use in breeding programs.

Two approaches are being used to increase the level of resistance:

1. diallel crosses of lines with intermediate levels of resistance; and
2. continued evaluation of the world collection to identify donor varieties with high levels of resistance.

We would appreciate hearing from scientists who may have recently identified additional sources of resistance to various stem borer species.

became hopperburned at 70 DT; shortly thereafter the alternate rows of IR1917-3-17 and the susceptible entries were damaged. Field damage was rated when plants in the adjacent susceptible row died and again at 95 DT (because BPH migrated from the dead susceptible plants to the surviving resistant plants).

In the greenhouse test, breeding lines from Indonesia, Thailand, Taiwan, Korea, and Japan lacked resistance to biotype 2 (see table), which is the prevalent biotype in parts of Indonesia and the Philippines

today. Only Indian and Sri Lankan entries had resistance to biotype 2. The photosensitive varieties from India and Sri Lanka such as Babawee, Rathu Heenati, and Ptb 33 (plus several not included in the table) and the lines CR157-380-292, CR 157-392-4, and IET 5122 were resistant to all three biotypes.

Field screening results indicated that biotype 2 was predominant. Field reactions were generally comparable with those in the greenhouse, but field

Greenhouse and field evaluation of the 1977 International Rice Brown Planthopper Nursery at IRRI

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The objectives of the International Rice Brown Planthopper Nursery (IRBPHN) are to determine the presence and distribution of BPH biotypes in Asia and to encourage the use of BPH-resistant germ plasm in rice improvement programs. The 1977 IRBPHN consists of 128 entries submitted by scientists in 7 countries and IRRI. Seed sets have been sent to 11 countries for testing.

We evaluated the 1977 IRBPHN against BPH biotypes 1,2, and 3 in the IRRI greenhouse, using the standard seedbox technique, and in the field. To induce high and evenly distributed BPH field populations, we alternated 4-m-long rows of the test entries and of the tungro-resistant but BPH-susceptible line IR1917-3-17. Seven rows of IR1917-3-17 were also planted as borders at each end of the alternating rows. The susceptible border rows were sprayed at 14-day intervals, beginning at 20 days after transplanting (DT), with 0.04% methyl parathion for the first two sprays and 0.025% Cypermethrin (WL43467), a synthetic pyrethroid, to induce a resurgence of the BPH. (If insecticide is not used to induce BPH populations, the population will generally be too low and poorly distributed for reliable readings of damage.) The border

Resistance of selected 1977 International Rice Brown Planthopper Nursery varieties in greenhouse and field studies. IRRI, 1977.

IRTP entry no.	Designation	Origin	Damage rating ^a					
			Greenhouse Biotype			Field		BPH ^d (no./hill)
			1	2	3	1st obser- vation ^b	95 DT ^c	
8	B2360-11-3-2-3	Indonesia	1	9	1	3	5	4852
11	Bogor 1	Indonesia	1	9	1	6	9	5707
14	Bogor 8	Indonesia	1	9	1	2	7	2731
34	BKNBR 1094-78-2	Thailand	1	8	3	5	7	3061
38	BR1030-11-2	Thailand	1	9	2	6	9	2356
47	Chianan shen yu 11	Taiwan	1	8	2	9	9	2415
49	CR94-13	India	1	3	8	1	5	3688
51	CR157-380-292	India	1	2	4	2	7	2825
52	CR157-392-284	India	2	4	8	2	3	2294
53	CR157-3924	India	1	3	4	2	5	2285
54	CR118-22-527	India	5	6	8	2	5	3271
56	CR179-1-717	India	1	2	8	2	3	2474
57	CR190-62-13	India	1	5	7	3	5	1060
63	IET 5118	India	3	7	5	2	5	2535
64	IET 5119	India	1	7	4	3	7	3110
65	IET 5120	India	3	4	5	2	3	853
66	IET 5122	India	1	2	2	1	3	655
69	IR8 M16	India	1	6	6	6	6	1299
71	IR26	IRRI	3	9	2	6	9	2314
74	Iri 329	Korea	1	8	2	9	9	1468
77	RD9	Thailand	1	9	4	5	9	1287
79	Taichung shen yu 221	Taiwan	1	8	2	7	9	1113
87	WX 324-8-3	Korea	1	9	2	9	9	1523
91	ARC 6650	India	3	2	9	3	3	606
93	ARC 14529	India	4	3	5	1	1	603
95	Babawee (bph 4 gene)	Sri Lanka	1	1	2	1	1	1449
119	Rathu Heenati (Bph 3 gene)	India	1	1	1	1	1	236
127	7512-146	Japan	1	8	6	8	9	1513
	<i>Susceptible check</i>							
	TN1	Taiwan	9	9	9	9	9	1528
	<i>Resistant check</i>							
	Mudgo (Bph 1 gene)	India	1	9	1	2	7	1102
	ASD 7 (bph 2 gene)	India	1	3	9	2	6	653
	Ptb 33	India	1	2	1	1	2	434

^aBased on the Standard Evaluation System rating: 0 = no damage; 9 = all plants dead. Greenhouse reading based on an average of 3 replicates and field ratings on 2 replicates.

^bFirst field observation ratings taken when the adjacent susceptible variety died.

^cDays after transplanting.

^dBPH count taken on hills at 80 DT with a D-Vac suction machine. Av. of 3 hills.